

“A CASE STUDY ON CONSTRAINTS PHASE BY THE MARKETERS IN MARKETING OF INSECTICIDE IN AMBALA DISTRICT OF HARYANA”

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Abstract

Under the direction of DR. Nitin Barker, "A Case Study on Consumer Buying Behaviour of Insecticide in Ambala District of Haryana" was completed. Ambala district was chosen on purpose since sugarcane output there is at a commercial level. To choose responders, a multi-stage random sampling approach was used. Naraingarh and Shehzadpur blocks in the Ambala district were specifically chosen out of a total of 06 blocks based on the percentage of respondents who used insecticide when growing sugarcane. Five communities were chosen at random. 120 sugarcane farmers were questioned, and they were afterwards categorised into five groups (marginal, small, semi-medium, medium, and large). 06 random villages were chosen at random to receive a certain number of responders. The data was gathered by a survey method according to a planned timetable. When conclusion was drawn there were it is seen that many constraints have occurred and identify the main constraints. The constraints were also discussed with growers and suggested some suitable measures. This present study pertains to the agriculture year 2022-2023.

Key Words- Saccharum officinarum, Farmers, Socio-economic group, Syngenta India Pvt. Ltd, Agri-inputs sampling, Agrochemical, Voliam Flexi, Consumer Buying Behaviour.

Introduction:

Sugarcane is a most important cash crop of India. It involves less risk and farmers are assured up to some extent about return even in adverse condition. Sugarcane provides raw material for the second largest agro-based industry after textile. The sugar industry is an instrumental in generating the sizable employment in the rural sector directly and through its ancillary units. It is estimated that about 50 million farmers and their dependents are engaged in the cultivation of sugarcane and about 0.5 million skilled and unskilled workers are engaged in sugar factories and its allied industries. The sugar industry in India has been a focal point for socio-economic development in the rural areas by mobilizing rural resources, generating employment and enhancing farm income.

There are 716 installed sugar factories (Co-operative-326, Private-347 & Public-43) in the country as on 31.01.2016, with sufficient crushing capacity to produce around 330 lakh MT of sugar.

Syngenta India Pvt. Ltd is a leading industry, focused on the quality of products in Agri-inputs business is a niche player in innovative agrochemicals with strong market share in insecticides. For research purpose multistage sampling method was used with personnel interviews and questionnaires with farmers, after conducting research it was found that large no. of farmer purchase sugarcane agrochemicals products from cooperatives because they provide credit facility. Dealers were keeping branded product for selling. Dealers as well as farmers preferred Syngenta agrochemicals on the basis of quality of the product. Almost all agrochemical companies generated demand from farmers by introducing various schemes, price discount and field demonstration to the farmers.

Voliam Flexi (Insecticide) are popular products of Syngenta India Pvt. Ltd. Based on above analysis on market functioning and consumer's buying behaviour, the company, should appoint sales manager and for improvement of sales of Syngenta Pvt. Ltd. in the studied area. Company should focus on cooperative stores for development of their business as well as increase more contact with farmer through their work force and management strategies.

Material And Methods:

Selection of District: There are 22 District in Haryana state and district name Panchkula, Ambala, Yamunanagar, Kurukshetra, Karnal, Kaithal, Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th variable by j th respondents.

N_j = Number of variables ranked by j th respondents.

Result And Discussion:

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Jind, Fatehbad, Hisar, Sonipat, Rohtak, Bhiwani, Jhajjar, Gurgaon, Mahendranagar, Mewat, Rawari, Sirsa, Faridabad, Panipat, Charkhi Dari, Palwal. Out of these, Ambala District of Haryana was selected purposively on the basis of maximum area under Sugarcane cultivation. Ambala district comprises of four sub-divisions, Ambala, Ambala Cantt, Barara and Naraingarh. Naraingarh sub-divisions comprises 1 tehsil, Naraingarh and 1 sub tehsil Shehzadpur. The significant towns in this district are Ambala Sadar, Ambala Cantt and Naraingarh.

Selection of Block: There are 06 Blocks in the district. Naraingarh and Shahzadpur block was selected purposively for the study based on the data from block offices because it occupies prestigious place in Sugarcane cultivation. Naraingarh being located 39 km from Ambala city, the district headquarters, 52 km of Chandigarh, the state capital, 144 km of Shimla, and 230 km of New Delhi. And Shahzadpur being located 30 km towards East from District headquarters Ambala.

Selection of Villages: There are a total of 100 villages in Naraingarh and Shahzadpur blocks. A list of all villages along with area under Sugarcane was obtained from the block office Naraingarh and Shahzadpur. Then all the villages were arranged in descending order on the basis of cultivated area of Sugarcane and 5 percent villages are randomly selected for the study.

Selection of Respondents: From the selected village list of all the Sugarcane cultivators obtained from the village development office in each selected village. For the selection of cultivators from families were listed and about 10% farmers were randomly selected from each village and then farmers were classified in to five groups.

Selection of Market: Primary and secondary market were selected randomly for data collection. Naraingarh and Shahzadpur were selected purposively. List of major market functionaries operating in the sample market and villages will be prepare.

Tools used for Analysis:

Garett's Ranking Techniques:

This is used to evaluate the problems faced by the sample respondents and to know preference among the given factors. In this method the respondents are asked to assign ranks to the given factors. The given ranks are converted into score values using the given formula.

Percent position = $100 (R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$

Constraints restricting against marketing of Insecticides

Sl.No.	Issues	Garett Score	Rank
1.	Loyal to other Product	82	VIII
2.	High Market Competition	70	VI
3.	Prices Fluctuation in Market	63	V
4.	Packaging Problem	58	III
5.	Derived Demand	52	X
6.	Fear of New Product	48	IV
7.	Tough Product Name	42	IX
8.	Fake Product in Market	37	VII
9.	Retailer Influence to Purchase other Product	30	II
10.	Product High Cost	18	I

This following table reveals about the constraints restricting against marketing of Insecticides in which Product high-cost rank I and Derived demand rank x.

Summary And Conclusion

Study reveals about the constraints restricting against marketing of Insecticides in which Product high-cost rank i, Retailer influence to purchase other product rank ii, packaging problem rank iii, Fear of new product rank iv, Prices fluctuation rank v, High market competition rank vi, Fake product in market rank vii, Loyal to other product rank viii, Tough product name rank ix and Derived demand rank x.

In current scenario and future of Insecticide have bright future. Farmers totally depends on the insecticide that show the increasing demand of the insecticide. Farmers not waste time on the field they want easy solutions for any problem of field therefore they use insecticide efficiently. Due to the use of the insecticide farmers yield more crops so they not stop to use the insecticide. Insecticide are less time taken, quick action on the target organisms and safe to use. Maximum farmers use the excess quantity of the insecticide but some farmers say that excess use of insecticide is harmful for the field and they use the insecticide only when it was very essential for the crop. According to farmer without insecticide in this time crop growing in effective manner is not possible because in every stage of the plant different type's insect are attacked so insecticide is important for farming purpose.

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